

Fe(III) and Co(III) Chelates of bis (2-OH, 4-CH₃), acetophenone) Ethylenediamine

L. D. DAVE & M. U. CYRIAC

Smt. Jadavben C. Sutaria P. G. Research Institute,

Bhavan's College, Dakor

Manuscript received 17 April 1973; revised 19 January 1974;

accepted 9 April 1974

THE Schiff base, H₂MAen, has been used previously for studying its metal chelates¹. Fe(III) and Co(III) complexes of this ligand have not been studied earlier.

Experimental

The ligand 2-OH, 4-CH₃ acetophenone ethylenediamine (H₂MAen) was prepared by refluxing the ketone 2-OH, 4-CH₃ acetophenone with ethylenediamine in alcohol for ~1 hr. The yellowish ligand which precipitates on cooling was recrystallised from chloroform. m.p 195°.

The ferric chelate was prepared by heating the ferric chloride for about half an hour with the ligand dissolved in alcohol. An acetate buffer was used to maintain pH between 6 and 6.5. The brown solid formed in hot was washed with water and alcohol and finally recrystallised from chloroform. It is insoluble in water and alcohol but dissolves in methanol, acetone, chloroform and DMF.

The cobaltic chelates was prepared by heating a mixture of cobalt chloride (1.4 g), ethylene diamine (3 ml) and the ketone 2-OH, 4-CH₃ acetophenone (6.5 ml) in 80% aqueous alcohol. Air was passed through the mixture and the heating continued for 2 hrs. After this, 10 ml. of 50% HCl was added and aeration continued for 24 hrs. The product obtained was filtered, washed with water and alcohol and dried at room temperature. The brown cobaltic chelate was found to be insoluble in water and alcohol but soluble in methanol, acetone, chloroform and DMF. It was recrystallised from chloroform.

The metal and chlorine were determined in each case by standard methods. The analysis seemed to point to the presence of two water molecules per metal ion and on this assumption the composition of the two complexes agreed with the presence of one ligand ion and one chloride ion. The complexes seemed to be M³⁺.(MAen).Cl.(H₂O)₂. Molecular weights, determined cryoscopically, showed that both the complexes were consistent with the presence of two water molecules. To confirm this, TGA of the complex was carried out on Linsei's Thermobalance. For the Fe³⁺ complex, the thermogram on 0.1 g. of complex showed a weight loss between 65° and 162°. This weight loss of 8.1 mgs corresponds to the presence of two water molecules (calculated, 8.01 mgs) in the complex. The second slow weight loss from 168° can be correlated with the presence of one chloride ion in the complex (wt. loss,

found : 7.2 mgs, calculated : 7.88 mgs). The decomposition of the complex starts from 285° and stops at 490°. The residue weighed 17.88 mgs as expected for Fe₂O₃. The DTA showed an endothermic peak at 125° confirming the presence of water in the complex. Co(II) complex gives similar thermogravimetric results. The molar conductance was measured in DMF solution using Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge. The values of molar conductances for the ferric and the cobaltic chelates were found to be 65.5 and 63.5 mhos cm² per mole for 10⁻³M solutions. The magnetic susceptibilities of the solid chelates were determined by the Gouy method. The electronic absorption spectra were measured in chloroform on spectronic-20. The IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs on Carl-Zeiss Jena 269642 I.R. type I.

Results and Discussion

Ferric complex : The magnetic moment is found to be 6.02 B.M. indicating five unpaired electrons. The molar conductance of 65.5 mhos cm² per mole seems to indicate a uni-univalent electrolyte. Values as low as 70 mhos cm² per mole are known² for such electrolytes. TGA indicates the presence of two water molecules in the complex. It is therefore, concluded that this complex is ionic in nature with chlorine bound ionically and that the complex cation is octahedrally surrounded, the Schiff base occupying four sites and the two water molecules occupying the remaining two, presumably trans, positions round a central Fe(III) ion. The I.R. spectrum of the complex shows bands at 450 cms⁻¹ and 630 cms⁻¹ which are assigned to M-O and M-N stretching frequencies³. A band at 750 cms⁻¹ could be due to the rocking vibration³ of coordinated water. There is a band at 3420 cms⁻¹ suggesting the presence of an -OH group. This is ascribed to the presence of water in the complex as no other -OH group is possible. The absorption spectrum of the complex shows a broad band in the visible with no clear maxima. The ligand has a strong absorption in the UV region with a long tail in the visible. A similar tail is also present in the complex giving strong general absorption in the visible. Such strong absorption is expected to swamp whatever bands are present as the latter would be very weak as they would be both spin- and Laporte-forbidden, the ground state being the only spin sextet.

Cobaltic chelate : The cobalt complex also has two water molecules in it as shown by analysis and TGA and DTA experiments. The conductivity of 63.5 mhos cm² per mole indicates a uni-uni electrolyte, chlorine being ionic. The magnetic moment is 0.64 B.M. which seems to be due to T.I.P.⁴ The complex is considered to have all the six electrons paired up with ¹A_g as the ground state, on an octahedral structure (ignoring the fact that all the near neighbours are not the same). The IR spectra of this complex are similar to those of the ferric complex. The electronic spectrum shows three absorption bands : 16130 cms⁻¹ (ε = 829), 17240 cms⁻¹ (964) and 30,100 cms⁻¹ (1762). The first two bands could be due to the transitions ¹T_{1g} ← ¹A_{1g} and ¹T_{2g} ← ¹A_{1g}

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOL. WT., MAGNETIC MOMENT AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA

Chelate	Metal %		Halogen %		Mol. wt.		μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Molar conductance mohs cm ² mol ⁻¹
	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.		
Fe.L.(H ₂ O) ₂ ⁺ Cl ⁻	12.55	12.4	8.0	7.90	453	499	6.02	65.5
Co.L.(H ₂ O) ₂ ⁺ Cl ⁻	12.85	13.0	8.0	7.85	450	452	0.64	63.5

respectively⁵. The band at 30100 cms⁻¹ could be a charge-transfer band. The general absorption in the visible is strong due to a long tail of the band at 30100 cms⁻¹.

Acknowledgement

We thank Prof. R. D. Patel of S. P. University for the use of equipment for magnetic, spectral and thermogravimetric measurements. We also thank Mr. J. T. D'Sa for his active help

References

1. L. D. DAVE, J. Z. PATEL and K. M. THANKEY, *Vidya* (B), Gujarat University Research Journal, 1973, 16, 35.
2. K. DEY, R. L. DE and K. C. RAY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 864.
3. KAZUO NAKAMOTO, "Infra-red Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, New York, pp. 146, 162 and 422.
4. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory, Inter Science Publishers Inc., New York, 1964, p. 279.
5. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, 1968, p. 301.

Preparation and Interconversion of Adducts of Copper(II) Benzoate Complex with Picolines and Quinolines

N. KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu,
Jammu-180001

Manuscript received 24 May 1973; revised 29 April 1974;
accepted 30 April 1974

COMPLEXES of metal carboxylates and their adducts with nitrogen donors have been studied in order to throw light on metal-metal bonding¹ and their anomalous magnetic properties²⁻⁵. Copper (II) benzoate is known to form 1:1 and 1:2 adducts with pyridine^{2,6-8} while 1:1 adduct has also been prepared with quinoline through ligand exchange⁶. It was, therefore considered interesting to prepare adducts of copper (II) benzoate with some more nitrogen heterocyclic ligands such as α -, β -, γ -picolines, quinoline and isoquinoline.

Interaction of copper (II) benzoate with the heterocyclic ligand in 1:1 molar ratio in acetone gives 1:1 adducts while 1:2 adducts are formed when a large excess of the ligand is used. 1:1 Adducts are stable while 1:2 adducts are thermally unstable and give stable 1:1 adducts on heating at 100°-150° or on refluxing in acetone. 1:1 Adducts, on the other hand, on treatment with excess of the ligand in an acetone medium give back 1:2 adducts.

Magnetic and spectral properties of these adducts are being investigated in order to ascertain their precise structures.

Experimental

Anhydrous copper (II) benzoate was prepared as reported earlier⁴. Nitrogen bases were purified by refluxing over potassium hydroxide followed by distillation under reduced pressure. Acetone was dried over fused potassium carbonate. The compounds were characterized by elemental analyses. Copper was estimated gravimetrically as cuprous thiocyanate⁹. Nitrogen was determined microanalytically. The analytical results are presented in Table 1.

Preparation of Adducts

All the adducts listed in Table 1 were prepared by the addition of an equimolar quantity or a large excess of the appropriate heterocyclic ligand to a 0.03M solution of anhydrous copper (II) Benzoate in acetone medium. The solution on standing deposited green or blue crystalline compounds depending on the amount of the ligand used. The compounds were filtered, washed with acetone or acetone containing a little of the appropriate ligand. 1:1 Green adducts were dried at 100°-110° in vacuo while the 1:2 blue adducts were dried at room temperature over conc sulphuric acid in a vacuum desiccator

Attempts to prepare 1:2 adducts of copper (II) benzoate with α -picoline and quinoline were unsuccessful.

Interconversion of 1:1 and 1:2 Adducts

1:2 Adducts on refluxing in acetone deposited corresponding 1:1 green adducts while 1:1 adducts on standing with a large excess of the ligand in acetone deposited 1:2 blue adducts. The compounds obtained were filtered, washed and dried as before. The purity of the samples was checked by metal analysis.